

Solution of a Conjecture on Skolem Mean Graph of Stars $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$

V.Balaji

(Department of Mathematics, Surya College of Engineering and Technology, Villupuram-605 652, India)

E-mail: pulibala70@gmail.com

Abstract: In this paper, we prove a conjecture that the three stars $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| < 4 + l$ for integers $l, m \geq 1$ and $l \leq m < n$.

Key Words: Smarandachely edge m -labeling f_S^* , Smarandachely super m -mean graph, skolem mean labeling, Skolem mean graph, star.

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§1. Introduction

All graphs in this paper are finite, simple and undirected. Terms not defined here are used in the sense of Harary [4]. A vertex labeling of G is an assignment $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, p + q\}$ be an injection. For a vertex labeling f , the induced Smarandachely edge m -labeling f_S^* for an edge $e = uv$, an integer $m \geq 2$ is defined by $f_S^*(e) = \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(v)}{m} \right\rceil$. Then f is called a Smarandachely super m -mean labeling if $f(V(G)) \cup \{f_S^*(e) : e \in E(G)\} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots, p + q\}$. Particularly, in the case of $m = 2$, we know that

$$f^*(e) = \begin{cases} \frac{f(u) + f(v)}{2} & \text{if } f(u) + f(v) \text{ is even;} \\ \frac{f(u) + f(v) + 1}{2} & \text{if } f(u) + f(v) \text{ is odd.} \end{cases}$$

Such a labeling is usually called a mean labeling. A graph that admits a Smarandachely super mean m -labeling is called a Smarandachely super m -mean graph, particularly, a skolem mean graph if $m = 2$ in [1]. It was proved that any path is a skolem mean graph, $K_{1,m}$ is not a skolem mean graph if $m \geq 4$, and the two stars $K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is a skolem mean graph if and only if $|m - n| \leq 4$. In [2], it was proved that the three star $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| = 4 + l$ for $l = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ and $l \leq m < n$. It is also shown in [2] that the three star $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is not a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| > 4 + l$ for $l = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, $n \geq l + m + 5$ and $l \leq m < n$, the four star $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| = 4 + 2l$ for $l = 2, 3, 4, \dots$, $m = 2, 3, 4, \dots$, $n = 2l + m + 4$ and $l \leq m < n$; the four star $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is not a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| > 4 + 2l$ for $l = 2, 3, 4, \dots$, $m = 2, 3, 4, \dots$, $n \geq 2l + m + 5$ and $l \leq m < n$; the four star $K_{1,1} \cup K_{1,1} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| = 7$ for

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$m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n = m + 7, 1 \leq m < n$, and the four star $K_{1,1} \cup K_{1,1} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is not a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| > 7$ for $m = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \geq m + 8$ and $1 \leq m < n$. In [3], the condition for a graph to be skolem mean is that $p \geq q + 1$.

§2. Main Theorem

Definition 2.1 *The three star is the disjoint union of $K_{1,l}, K_{1,m}$ and $K_{1,n}$ for integers $l, m, n \geq 1$. Such a graph is denoted by $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$.*

Theorem 2.2 *If $l \leq m < n$, the three star $K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$ is a skolem mean graph if $|m - n| < 4 + l$ for integers $l, m \geq 1$.*

Proof Consider the graph $G = K_{1,l} \cup K_{1,m} \cup K_{1,n}$. Let $\{u\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq l\}, \{v\} \cup \{v_j : 1 \leq j \leq m\}$ and $\{w\} \cup \{w_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ be the vertices of G . Then G has $l + m + n + 3$ vertices and $l + m + n$ edges. We have $V(G) = \{u, v, w\} \cup \{u_i : 1 \leq i \leq l\} \cup \{v_j : 1 \leq j \leq m\} \cup \{w_k : 1 \leq k \leq n\}$. The proof is divided into four cases following.

Case 1 Let $l \leq m < n$ where $n = l + m + 3$ for integers $l, m \geq 1$. We prove such graph G is a skolem mean graph. The required vertex labeling $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, l + m + n + 3\}$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u) &= 1, & f(v) &= 3; \\ f(w) &= l + m + n + 3; \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 3 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq l; \\ f(v_j) &= 2l + 2j + 3 \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m; \\ f(w_k) &= 2k \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq n - 1 \text{ and} \\ f(w_n) &= l + m + n + 2. \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding edge labels are as follows:

The edge labels of uu_i is $i + 2$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$, vv_j is $l + j + 3$ for $1 \leq j \leq m$ and ww_k is $\frac{2k + l + m + n + 3}{2}$ for $1 \leq k \leq n - 1$. Also, the edge label of ww_n is $l + m + n + 3$. Therefore, the induced edge labels of G are distinct. Hence G is a skolem mean graph.

Case 2 Let $l \leq m < n$ where $n = l + m + 2$ for integers $l, m \geq 1$. We prove that G is a skolem mean graph. The required vertex labeling $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, l + m + n + 3\}$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u) &= 1; & f(v) &= 2; & f(w) &= l + m + n + 3; \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 2 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq l; \\ f(v_j) &= 2l + 2j + 2 \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m; \\ f(w_k) &= 2k + 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq n - 1 \text{ and} \\ f(w_n) &= l + m + n + 2. \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding edge labels are as follows:

The edge labels of uu_i is $i + 2$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$; vv_j is $l + j + 2$ for $1 \leq j \leq m$ and ww_k is $\frac{2k + l + m + n + 4}{2}$ for $1 \leq k \leq n - 1$. Also, the edge label of ww_n is $l + m + n + 3$. Therefore, the induced edge labels of G are distinct. Hence the graph G is a skolem mean graph.

Case 3 Let $l \leq m < n$ where $n = l + m + 1$ for integers $l, m \geq 1$. In this case, the required vertex labeling $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, l + m + n + 3\}$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u) &= 1; f(v) = 2; f(w) = l + m + n + 3; \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq l; \\ f(v_j) &= 2l + 2j + 1 \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m; \\ f(w_k) &= 2k + 2 \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq n - 1 \text{ and} \\ f(w_n) &= l + m + n + 2. \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding edge labels are as follows:

The edge labels of uu_i is $i + 1$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$; vv_j is $l + j + 2$ for $1 \leq j \leq m$ and ww_k is $\frac{2k + l + m + n + 5}{2}$ for $1 \leq k \leq n - 1$. Also, the edge label of ww_n is $l + m + n + 3$. Therefore, the induced edge labels of G are distinct. Therefore, G is a skolem mean graph.

Case 4 Let $l \leq m < n$ where $n = l + m$ for integers $l, m \geq 1$. We prove such graph G is a skolem mean graph. In this case, the required vertex labeling $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, l + m + n + 3\}$ is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u) &= 1; f(v) = 3; f(w) = l + m + n + 3; \\ f(u_i) &= 2i \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq l; \\ f(v_j) &= 2l + 2j \text{ for } 1 \leq j \leq m; \\ f(w_k) &= 2k + 3 \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq n - 1 \text{ and} \\ f(w_n) &= l + m + n + 2. \end{aligned}$$

Calculation shows the corresponding edge labels are as follows:

The edge labels of uu_i is $i + 1$ for $1 \leq i \leq l$; vv_j is $l + j + 2$ for $1 \leq j \leq m$ and ww_k is $\frac{2k + l + m + n + 6}{2}$ for $1 \leq k \leq n - 1$. Also, the edge label of ww_n is $l + m + n + 3$. Therefore, the induced edge labels of G are distinct and G is a skolem mean graph.

Combining these discussions of Cases 1 – 4, we know that G is a skolem mean graph. \square

References

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